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Heat transfer questions in fire science

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Preface

ME2 Heat transfer is definitely one of the most fascinating and useful courses taught during the second year. It is undoubtedly a must for any mechanical engineer. Nevertheless, until the 2020-2021 academic year, one of the most important fields of this subject was left out of the syllabus: fire science. Fire is a complicated phenomenon that introduces itself in the life of every engineer sooner or later. It is therefore crucial to know how to deal with fire and be able to conduct an analysis (even a basic one) concerning its behaviour. This document consists of a collection of fire science question, accompanied by detailed solutions and explanations, that are going to integrate the Heat transfer course taught in ME2.

Most of the fire related questions are taken from the *Principles of heat and mass transfer - global edition* (Incropera, 2017) and *An Introduction to Fire Dynamics* (Drysdale, 2011) textbooks and cover topics included in the present syllabus. Some other sources were also consulted (see **Bonus** and **References** sections). Solutions were written out for each question following the schematic learnt in class, as well as the one suggested by Incropera himself. In this way, students should find it easy to understand what exactly is the thought process behind every step or calculation and fully understand how to approach different types of fire related questions.

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FIRE RELATED QUESTIONS

Question 1.64 f

A double-glazed, glass fire screen is inserted between a wood-burning fireplace and the interior of a room. The screen consists of two vertical glass plates that are separated by a space through which room air may flow (the space is open at the top and bottom). Identify the heat transfer processes associated with the fire screen.

Incropera, 2017

Question 1.64 f - SOLUTION

The scenario can be represented in the following way:

As it can be understood from the schematic above, the relevant heat transfer processes concerning the two glass screens are:

Questions for ME2 Heat transfer

- $q_{rad,1}$ = radiation from flames and cavity wall, portions of which are absorbed and transmitted by the two panes.
- $q_{rad,2}$ = Emission from inner surface of inner pane to cavity.
- $q_{rad,3}$ = Net radiation exchange between outer surface of inner pane and inner surface of outer pane.
- $q_{rad,4}$ = Net radiation exchange between outer surface of outer pane and walls of room.
- $q_{conv,1}$ = Convection between cavity gases and inner pane.
- $q_{conv,2}$ = Convection across air space between panes.
- $q_{conv,3}$ = Convection from outer surface to room air.
- $q_{cond,1}$ = Conduction across inner pane.
- $q_{cond,2}$ = Conduction across outer pane.

Note that all convection processes are buoyancy driven (free convection).

Question 3.20

A firefighter's protective clothing, referred to as a turnout coat, is typically constructed as an ensemble of three layers separated by air gaps, as shown schematically.

Incropera, 2017

Representative dimensions and thermal conductivities for the layers are as follows.

Layer	Thickness (mm)	k (W/m · K)
Shell (s)	0.8	0.047
Moisture barrier (mb)	0.55	0.012
Thermal liner (tl)	3.5	0.038

Incropera, 2017

The air gaps between the layers are 1 mm thick, and heat is transferred by conduction and radiation exchange through the stagnant air. The linearized radiation coefficient for a gap may be approximated as, $h_{rad} = \epsilon\sigma(T_1 + T_2)(T_1^2 + T_2^2) \approx 4\sigma T_{avg}^3$ (assume $\epsilon = 1$), where T_{avg} represents the average temperature of the surfaces comprising the gap, and the radiation flux across the gap may be expressed as $q'' = h_{rad}(T_1 + T_2)$.

(a) Represent the turnout coat by a thermal circuit, labelling all the thermal resistances. Calculate and tabulate the thermal resistances per unit area ($m^2 \cdot K/W$) for each of the layers, as well as for the conduction and radiation processes in the gaps. Assume that a value of $T_{avg} = 470$ K may be used to approximate the radiation resistance of both gaps. Comment on the relative magnitudes of the resistances.

(b) For a *pre-flash-over* environment in which firefighters often work, the typical radiant heat flux on the fire-side of the turnout coat is 0.25 W/cm². What is the outer

surface temperature of the turnout coat if the inner surface temperature is 66 °C, a condition that would result in burn injury?

[The step-by-step solution of this question was recorded and can be found following this link: Question 3.20 - stream cast]

Question 3.20 - SOLUTION

(a) The first task consists of visualising the scenario and transforming the system described in the exercise in an equivalent thermal circuit. Before doing so, it is essential to remember that the exercise asks to account for the thermal resistances of both conduction and radiation. This of course concerns only the two air gaps of the system, as it is reasonable to assume that the solid parts (shell, moisture barrier and thermal liner) exert resistance only against conduction. Having said that, the system can be simplified in the following way:

It is crucial to bear in mind that the resistances of the two air gaps regard different mode of heat transfer (radiation and conduction). Therefore, $R''_{air,cond}$ and $R''_{air,rad}$ cannot be simply added (i.e in *series*), yet they have to be treated as two parallel branches which both contribute to the total resistance R''_{tot} . [For more information on this see example 3.1 in the *Incropera* textbook].

Now all the thermal resistances must be evaluated through the following formulas.

$$R''_{cond} = \frac{L}{k}$$

$$R''_{rad} = \frac{1}{h_{rad}} = \frac{1}{4\sigma T_{avg}^3}$$

$$\frac{1}{R''_{tot,gap}} = \frac{1}{R''_{cond}} + \frac{1}{R''_{rad}}$$

At this stage, the only datum missing in order to tabulate all the resistances of the system is the conductivity of the air gaps at $T_{avg} = 470$ K, which can be considered to be $k = 0.0387$ W/m · K.

Thermal resistances of each layer of the system

	Shell	Air gap	Barrier	Air gap	Liner	TOTAL
R''_{cond} [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	0.01702	0.0259	0.04583	0.0259	0.00921	-
R''_{rad} [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	-	0.04246	-	0.04246	-	-
$R''_{tot,gap}$ [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	-	0.01611	-	0.11611	-	-
R''_{tot} [$m^2 \cdot K/W$]	-	-	-	-	-	0.1043

COMMENT: the most protective layers of the firefighter's clothing are the moisture barrier (whose thermal resistance is almost three times larger than the one of the shell and the small air gaps) and the liner. Note also that the air gaps exhibit a higher resistance to radiation rather than conduction.

(b) If the heat flux through the coat is 0.25 W/cm^2 , the fire-side surface temperature T_o can be obtained from the heat rate equation expressed in terms of R''_{tot} .

$$q'' = \frac{(T_o - T_i)}{R''_{tot}}$$

$$T_o = 66^\circ\text{C} + 0.25 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot 10^4 \cdot 0.1043 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W} = 327^\circ\text{C}$$

Question 5.14

Carbon steel (AISI 1010) shafts of 80 mm diameter are heat treated in a gas-fired furnace whose gases are at 1200 K and provide a convection coefficient of 125 W/m²·K. If the shafts enter the furnace at 300 K, how long must they remain in the furnace to achieve a centerline temperature of 800 K?

Question 5.14 - SOLUTION

This is a problem regarding the transient behaviour of the temperature distribution in a solid. Therefore the first step consists of evaluating the Biot number associated with the solid. To do so, it is necessary to evaluate the properties of the steel at $T_{avg} = (800 \text{ K} + 300 \text{ K}) \div 2 = 550 \text{ K}$: $\rho = 7832 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $k = 51.2 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m/K}$, $c = 541 \text{ J/Kg}$, $\alpha = 1.21 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

Remembering that the characteristic length of a cylinder can be considered to be $L_c = r/2$ (see the top of page 259 of the *Incropera* textbook if you do not understand this), the Biot number of the solid is:

$$Bi = \frac{h \cdot L_c}{k} = \frac{(125 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}) \cdot (0.04/2 \text{ m})}{51.2 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m/K}} = 0.039$$

As $Bi < 0.1$, the **lumped capacitance** assumption can be assumed to be valid. Therefore, the temperature distribution in the solid can be assumed to be uniform throughout and the following equation can be employed:

$$\frac{T - T_\infty}{T_i - T_\infty} = e^{-\left(\frac{hA_s}{\rho V c}\right) \cdot t} = e^{-\left(\frac{2h}{\rho r c}\right) \cdot t}$$

The formula above must then be rearranged to express t (the variable we are interested in) in terms of the other parameters.

$$t = -\ln\left(\frac{T - T_\infty}{T_i - T_\infty}\right) \cdot \frac{\rho r c}{2h}$$

By subbing in the values, it is found that the time required for the centerline of the solid to reach 800 K is $t = 549.8 \text{ s}$.

Question 5.37

Annealing is a process by which steel is reheated and then cooled to make it less brittle. Consider the reheat stage for a 125-mm-thick steel plate ($\rho = 7830 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $c = 550 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$, $k = 48 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$), which is initially at a uniform temperature of $T_i = 150^\circ\text{C}$ and is to be heated to a minimum temperature of 500°C . Heating is effected in a gas-fired furnace, where products of combustion at $T_\infty = 850^\circ\text{C}$ maintain a convection coefficient of $h = 200 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$ on both surfaces of the plate. How long should the plate be left in the furnace?

Question 5.37 - SOLUTION

The system can be represented by the following schematic:

The first step in exercises where the temperature changes over time is always evaluating the Biot number of the solid. Remember that, in this case, the characteristic length associated with the solid is $L_c = 0.0625 \text{ m}$ (see page 259).

$$Bi = \frac{h \cdot L_c}{k} = \frac{(200 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}) \cdot (0.0625 \text{ m})}{48 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m/K}} = 0.26$$

As $Bi > 0.1$, the **lumped capacitance** assumption is not valid and thus *Fourier* exact solutions should be used. The question asks for the minimum time the slab should be left in the furnace to reach a uniform temperature of 500°C : this implies that we should find the time for the centerline temperature to reach the specified value as the lowest temperature in the slab will always be at the midplane ($x^* = 0$). We can employ the exact solutions suggested in **Chapter 5** of the *Incropera* book because we are dealing with a situation of symmetrically cooled solid (the same scenario considered in the book). Assuming that $Fo > 0.2$, we can use the one-term approximation for the transient thermal response of a plane wall:

$$C \approx 1.0396$$

$$\zeta \approx 0.488 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta^* = C \cdot e^{-\zeta^2 Fo} \cdot \cos(\zeta x^*)$$

Remembering that $Fo = (\alpha t)/L_c^2$, rearranging for t and subbing in the values:

$$\theta^* = \frac{500^\circ\text{C} - 850^\circ\text{C}}{150^\circ\text{C} - 850^\circ\text{C}} = 0.5$$

$$t = -\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\theta^*}{C} \cdot L_c^2\right)}{\zeta^2 \alpha} = -\frac{\ln\left(\frac{0.5}{1.0396}\right) \cdot (0.0625 \text{ m})^2}{(0.488 \text{ rad})^2 \frac{48 \text{ W/m}}{7830 \text{ kg/m}^3 \cdot 550 \text{ J/kg}}} = 1077.35 \text{ s}$$

You can now check whether assuming that $Fo > 0.2$ was sensible or not.

Question 5.106

Steel-reinforced concrete pillars are used in the construction of large buildings. Structural failure can occur at high temperatures due to a fire because of softening of the metal core. Consider a 200-mm-thick composite pillar consisting of a central steel core (50 mm thick) sandwiched between two 75-mm-thick concrete walls. The pillar is at a uniform initial temperature of $T_i = 27^\circ\text{C}$ and is suddenly exposed to combustion products at $T_\infty = 900^\circ\text{C}$, $h = 40 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$ on both exposed surfaces. The surroundings temperature is also 900°C .

(a) Using an implicit finite difference method with $\Delta x = 10 \text{ mm}$ and $\Delta t = 100 \text{ s}$, determine the temperature of the exposed concrete surface and the center of the steel plate at $t = 10,000 \text{ s}$. Steel properties are: $k_s = 55 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$, $\rho_s = 7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and $c_s = 450 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$. Concrete properties are: $k_c = 1.4 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$, $\rho_c = 2300 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $c_s = 880 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$, and $\epsilon = 0.90$. Plot the maximum and minimum concrete temperatures along with the maximum and minimum steel temperatures over the duration $0 \leq t \leq 10,000 \text{ s}$.

(b) Repeat part (a) but account for a thermal contact resistance of $R''_{t,c} = 0.20 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$ at the concrete steel interface.

(c) At $t = 10,000 \text{ s}$, the fire is extinguished, and the surroundings and ambient temperatures return to $T_\infty = T_{surr} = 27^\circ\text{C}$. Using the same convection heat transfer coefficient and emissivity as in parts (a) and (b), determine the maximum steel temperature and the critical time at which the maximum steel temperature occurs for cases with and without the contact resistance. Plot the concrete surface temperature, the concrete temperature adjacent to the steel, and the steel temperatures over the duration $10,000 \leq t \leq 20,000 \text{ s}$.

Question 5.106 - SOLUTION

The domain should be discretised as shown in the below image:

Note that the nodes that should be considered for the analysis are found right in the middle of the chosen volumes. Bear this in mind as it is going to be crucial for later.

(a) For every discretised volume, energy balances (per unit area!) must be carried out.

$$\dot{E}_{st} = \dot{E}_{in} - \dot{E}_{out} + \dot{E}_g$$

$$\rho_c c_c \frac{\Delta x}{2} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = q''_{conv,rad} + q''_{cond}$$

Of course, this is a general expression: for each node and scenario there may or may not be some of the terms appearing above. Do not get confused: this is not the same as the heat diffusion equation! That is why we do not have any second order partial differential equations.

Let's start by analysing the first node, for which both $q''_{conv,rad}$ and q''_{cond} terms appear. By discretising the formula above the following using an **implicit** difference method (for time and space), the following expression should be obtained:

$$\rho_c c_c \frac{\Delta x}{2} \frac{T_1^{p+1} - T_1^p}{\Delta t} = (h_{conv} + h_{rad})(T_\infty - T_1^{p+1}) + \frac{k_c (T_2^{p+1} - T_1^{p+1})}{\Delta x}$$

where $h_{rad} = \epsilon \sigma (T_{surr} + T_1)(T_{surr}^2 + T_1^2)$ and $T_{surr} = T_\infty$.

For nodes 2-7, instead, there is no $q_{conv,rad}$ term and conduction occurs on both the left and right side of the discretised volumes.

$$\rho_c c_c \Delta x \frac{T_i^{p+1} - T_i^p}{\Delta t} = \frac{k_c (T_{i-1}^{p+1} - T_i^{p+1})}{\Delta x} + \frac{k_c (T_{i+1}^{p+1} - T_i^{p+1})}{\Delta x}$$

For node 8, the presence of the contact resistance must be accounted for (ignore this for part (a), it will be useful for part (b)).

$$\rho_c c_c \Delta x \frac{T_8^{p+1} - T_8^p}{\Delta t} = \frac{(T_9^{p+1} - T_8^{p+1})}{R''_{tot}} + \frac{k_c (T_7^{p+1} - T_8^{p+1})}{\Delta x}$$

where $R''_{tot} = \frac{\Delta x/2}{k_c} + \frac{\Delta x/2}{k_s} + R''_{t,c}$.

!!! Remember the signs of heat going into and out of the control volumes and that $q''_{cond} = -k \nabla T$.

The expression for node 9 is almost the same as the one for node 8, yet the properties are the ones of steel.

$$\rho_s c_s \Delta x \frac{T_9^{p+1} - T_9^p}{\Delta t} = \frac{(T_8^{p+1} - T_9^{p+1})}{R''_{tot}} + \frac{k_s (T_{10}^{p+1} - T_9^{p+1})}{\Delta x}$$

For node 10 the following formula should be employed:

$$\rho_s c_s \Delta x \frac{T_{10}^{p+1} - T_{10}^p}{\Delta t} = \frac{k_s (T_9^{p+1} - T_{10}^{p+1})}{\Delta x} + \frac{k_s (T_{11}^{p+1} - T_{10}^{p+1})}{\Delta x}$$

Finally, for node 11:

$$\rho_s c_s \frac{\Delta x}{2} \frac{T_{11}^{p+1} - T_{11}^p}{\Delta t} = \frac{k_s (T_{10}^{p+1} - T_{11}^{p+1})}{\Delta x}$$

If you notice, only half of the domain has been discretised because the symmetry of the problem was exploited. The equations above must be solved via Gaussian elimination or Jacobi / Gauss Seidel iterative method (try it on python) and the following result should be obtained:

As the graph points out, the steel block is characterised by an almost a uniform temperature due to its high conductivity. That is why one line is enough to describe how $T_{max,steel}$ and $T_{min,steel}$ evolve with time. The same is not true for concrete, which, due to its low conductivity, exhibits two distinct $T_{max,concr}$ and $T_{min,concr}$ lines.

(b) If $R''_{t,c}$ is included, the following results are obtained.

The features of this graph are almost the same of the one in part (a), with steel being treated as isothermal. However, it is interesting to note that the contact resistance influences $T_{max,steel}$ deeply by decreasing it substantially.

(c) Using the nodal temperatures at 10.000 s yielded by the previous simulations as starting points, the new analysis is carried out with $T_{\infty} = T_{surr} = 300$ K. The critical time needed for steel to reach its maximum temperature without $R''_{t,c}$ is $t_{crit} = 11.100$ s with $T_{max,steel} = 890.6$ K. The critical time needed for steel to reach its maximum temperature with the addition of $R''_{t,c}$ is $t_{crit} = 16.100$ s with $T_{max,steel} = 578.7$ K.

FINAL COMMENT: note that the influence of the contact resistance is important not only for the maximum temperature experienced by the block of steel yet also for the critical time to reach $T_{max,steel}$. Nevertheless, with or without $R''_{t,c}$, $T_{max,steel}$ is reached always after the fire is extinguished, as warm temperatures within the concrete slowly propagate (due to the low conductivity) into the steel plate. Therefore firefighters need to be very cautious after the fire has extinguished as structural failure may occur hours after the last flames have died out.

Question 7.52

An aluminum transmission line with a diameter of 20 mm has an electrical resistance of $R'_{elec} = 2.636 \cdot 10^{-4} \Omega/\text{m}$ and carries a current of 700 A. The line is subjected to frequent and severe cross winds, increasing the probability of contact between adjacent lines, thereby causing sparks and creating a potential fire hazard for nearby vegetation. The remedy is to insulate the line, but with the adverse effect of increasing the conductor operating temperature.

- (a) Calculate the conductor temperature when the air temperature is 20°C and the line is subjected to cross flow with a velocity of 10 m/s.
- (b) Calculate the conductor temperature for the same conditions, but with a 2-mm-thick insulation having a thermal conductivity of 0.15 W/m·K.
- (c) Calculate and plot the temperatures of the bare and insulated conductors for wind velocities in the range from 2 to 20 m/s. Comment on features of the curves and the effect of the wind velocity on the conductor temperatures.

HINT: due to the geometry of the system, use [equation 7.54](#) on page 451 of the textbook.

[The step-by-step solution of this question was recorded and can be found following this link: [Question 7.52 - stream cast](#)]

Question 7.52 - SOLUTION

- (a) The first step consists of carrying out a basic energy balance on the cable (remembering that we are interested in the steady state $\dot{E}_{st} = 0$):

$$0 = \dot{E}_{in} - \dot{E}_{out} + \dot{E}_g$$

$$0 - q_{cv}' + \dot{q}A_c = 0$$

where $A_c = \pi D^2/4$ and the generation rate is:

$$\dot{q} = I^2 R'_e / A_c = ((700 \text{ A})^2 \cdot 2.636 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ } \Omega/\text{m}) / \left(\frac{\pi(0.02\text{m})^2}{4} \right) = 4.111 \cdot 10^5 \text{ W/m}^3$$

The convection term can also be found as it can be expressed as:

$$q_{cv}' = \frac{T_{c,bare} - T_\infty}{R'_t}$$

where $R'_t = 1/(\overline{h}_D \cdot \pi D)$. \overline{h}_D can be found through the Churchill-Bernstein equation relating the Nusselt number to the Prandtl and Reynolds one of the fluid (use a film temperature around 350 K and adjust it though iterative methods if you see that the answer you get is far off from your guess).

$$\overline{Nu}_D = \frac{\overline{h}_D D}{k} = 0.3 + \frac{0.62 Re_D^{0.5} Pr^{1/3}}{[1 + (0.4/Pr)^{2/3}]^{1/3}} \cdot [1 + (\frac{Re_D}{282000})^{5/8}]^{4/5}$$

Subbing in the correct values, it is determined that: $Re_D = 1.214 \cdot 10^4$, $\overline{Nu}_D = 59.6$, $\overline{h}_D = 79.6 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and finally $R'_t = 0.1998 \text{ m} \cdot \text{K/W}$. Therefore:

$$T_{c,bare} = 4.111 \cdot 10^5 \text{ W/m}^3 \cdot A_c \cdot R'_t + T_\infty = 45.8^\circ\text{C}$$

(b) The thought process and the equations used for this part are exactly the same as part (a), yet the diameter of the tube changes ($D_{new} = D + 2 \cdot t = 24 \text{ mm}$) and so does the thermal resistance R'_t .

$$R'_t = \frac{1}{(\overline{h}_{D_{new}} \cdot \pi D)} + \frac{\ln(\frac{D_{new}}{D})}{2\pi k}$$

With these new expression, the following results should be obtained: $Re_D = 1.468 \cdot 10^4$, $\overline{Nu}_D = 66.3$, $\overline{h}_D = 73.6 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and finally $R'_t = 0.3736 \text{ m} \cdot \text{K/W}$. Therefore $T_c = 68.3^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) (Use pyhton/matlab for this).

FINAL COMMENT = the effect of the 2 mm insulation layer is to increase the temperature of the cable by 22°C. We did not account for a change in electrical resistivity of the cable as a result of the increase in temperature, yet it must be noted that the dissipation loss (I^2R) increases too as T_{cable} rises. An interesting peculiarity shown in the graph is the conductor temperature, which is inversely proportional to the wind speed.

Question 8.74

It is common practice to recover waste heat from an oil or gas-fired furnace by using the exhaust gases to preheat the combustion air. A device commonly used for this purpose consists of a concentric pipe arrangement for which the exhaust gases are passed through the inner pipe, while the cooler combustion air flows through an annular passage around the pipe.

Incropera, 2017

Consider conditions for which there is a uniform heat transfer rate per unit length, $q'_i = 1.25 \cdot 10^5 \text{ W/m}$, from the exhaust gases to the pipe inner surface, while air flows through the annular passage at a rate of $\dot{m}_a = 2.1 \text{ kg/s}$. The thin-walled inner pipe is of diameter $D_i = 2 \text{ m}$, while the outer pipe, which is well insulated from the surroundings, is of diameter $D_o = 2.05 \text{ m}$. The air properties may be taken to be $c_p = 1030 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$, $\mu = 270 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ N} \cdot \text{s/m}^2$, $k = 0.041 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$, and $Pr = 0.68$.

- If air enters at $T_{a,1} = 300 \text{ K}$ and $L = 7 \text{ m}$, what is the air outlet temperature $T_{a,2}$?
- If the airflow is fully developed throughout the annular region, what is the temperature of the inner pipe at the inlet ($T_{s,i,1}$) and outlet ($T_{s,i,2}$) sections of the device? What is the outer surface temperature $T_{s,o,1}$ at the inlet?

NOTE: if you find yourself stuck, especially when calculating the heat transfer coefficients, look at pages **510-512** of the textbook.

Question 8.74 - SOLUTION

(a) This part can be solved by conducting a simple energy balance on the air.

$$q'_i L = \dot{m}_a c_{p,a} (T_{a,2} - T_{a,1})$$

Rearranging the equation for $T_{a,2}$ and inputting the correct values in the formula, it should be found that $T_{a,2} = 704.5$ K.

(b) The first step of this part consists of evaluating the hydraulic diameter of the system which is defined as:

$$D_h = \frac{4A_c}{P} = \frac{4(\pi/4)(D_o^2 - D_i^2)}{\pi(D_o + D_i)} = D_o - D_i$$

where A_c and P are respectively the *flow cross-sectional area* and *wetted perimeter*. Once the hydraulic diameter is calculated, the Reynolds number of the flow must be determined:

$$Re_D = \frac{\rho u_m D_h}{\mu} = \frac{4\dot{m}}{\pi(D_o + D_i)\mu} = \frac{4 \cdot (2.1 \text{ kg/s})}{\pi \cdot (4.05 \text{ m}) \cdot 270 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ N} \cdot \text{s/m}^2} = 24452$$

As $Re > 10000$, the flow is turbulent. Therefore equation 8.60 from page **502** in the textbook can be used (considering we are looking at a heating scenario) to evaluate the convective heat transfer coefficients (note that as $D_i/D_o \approx 1$ it is reasonable to assume that $h_i \approx h_o$):

$$h_i \approx h_o \approx \frac{k}{D_h} 0.023 Re_D^{4/5} Pr^{0.4} = \frac{0.041 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}}{0.05 \text{ m}} \cdot 0.023 \cdot (24452)^{4/5} \cdot (0.68)^{0.4} = 52 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$$

Now equation 8.67 should be employed to calculate $T_{s,i,1}$:

$$q_i'' = \frac{q'_i}{\pi D_i} = 19900 \text{ W/m}^2$$

$$(T_{s,i} - T_m) = \frac{q_i''}{h_i} = 383 \text{ K}$$

Adding 383 K to $T_{a,2}$ and $T_{a,1}$ we get: $T_{s,i,1} = 683$ K and $T_{s,i,2} = 1087.5$ K.

Finally, as the outer surface is insulated so that $q_o'' = 0$:

$$(T_{s,o,1} - T_m) = \frac{q_o''}{h_i} = 383 \text{ K} = 0$$

Hence, $T_{s,o,1} = T_{a,1} = 300$ K. Remember that $T_m = T_{a,1}$ at the inlet and $T_m = T_{a,2}$ at the outlet.

Example 9.2

EXAMPLE 9.2

A glass-door firescreen, used to reduce exfiltration of room air through a chimney, has a height of 0.71 m and a width of 1.02 m and reaches a temperature of 232°C. If the room temperature is 23°C, estimate the convection heat rate from the fireplace to the room.

SOLUTION

Known: Glass screen situated in fireplace opening.

Find: Heat transfer by convection between screen and room air.

Schematic:

Assumptions:

1. Screen is at a uniform temperature T_s .
2. Room air is quiescent.
3. Ideal gas.
4. Constant properties.

Properties: Table A.4, air ($T_f = 400$ K): $k = 33.8 \times 10^{-3}$ W/m·K, $\nu = 26.4 \times 10^{-6}$ m²/s, $\alpha = 38.3 \times 10^{-6}$ m²/s, $Pr = 0.690$, $\beta = (1/T_f) = 0.0025$ K⁻¹.

Incropera, 2017

Analysis: The rate of heat transfer by free convection from the panel to the room is given by Newton's law of cooling

$$q = \bar{h}A_s(T_s - T_\infty)$$

where \bar{h} may be obtained from knowledge of the Rayleigh number. Using Equation 9.25,

$$\begin{aligned} Ra_L &= \frac{g\beta(T_s - T_\infty)L^3}{\alpha\nu} \\ &= \frac{9.8 \text{ m/s}^2 \times 0.0025 \text{ K}^{-1} \times (232 - 23)^\circ\text{C} \times (0.71 \text{ m})^3}{38.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s} \times 26.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}} = 1.813 \times 10^9 \end{aligned}$$

and from Equation 9.23 it follows that transition to turbulence occurs on the panel. The appropriate correlation is then given by Equation 9.26

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{Nu}_L &= \left\{ 0.825 + \frac{0.387 Ra_L^{1/6}}{[1 + (0.492/Pr)^{9/16}]^{8/27}} \right\}^2 \\ \overline{Nu}_L &= \left\{ 0.825 + \frac{0.387(1.813 \times 10^9)^{1/6}}{[1 + (0.492/0.690)^{9/16}]^{8/27}} \right\}^2 = 147 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\bar{h} = \frac{\overline{Nu}_L \cdot k}{L} = \frac{147 \times 33.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}}{0.71 \text{ m}} = 7.0 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$$

and

$$q = 7.0 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K} (1.02 \times 0.71) \text{ m}^2 (232 - 23)^\circ\text{C} = 1060 \text{ W}$$

Question 11.1

In a fire-tube boiler, hot products of combustion flowing through an array of thin-walled tubes are used to boil water flowing over the tubes. At the time of installation, the overall heat transfer coefficient was $400 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$. After 1 year of use, the inner and outer tube surfaces are fouled, with corresponding fouling factors of $R'_{f,i} = 0.0015$ and $R'_{f,o} = 0.0005 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$, respectively. Should the boiler be scheduled for cleaning of the tube surfaces?

[The step-by-step solution of this question was recorded and can be found following this link: [Question 11.1 - stream cast](#)]

Question 11.1 - SOLUTION

The overall heat transfer coefficient can be expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{U} = \frac{1}{h} + R''_{f,i} + R''_{f,o} = \frac{1}{400 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}} + 0.0005 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W} + 0.0015 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K/W}$$

By solving the above equation, it is found that $U = 222 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$.

COMMENT: fouling is a phenomenon that must be taken into account when designing heat exchangers as it decreases the overall heat transfer coefficient and hence the efficiency of the system.

**ADDITIONAL FIRE RELATED
QUESTIONS - BONUS**

Question 5.72

A thick oak wall, initially at 25°C, is suddenly exposed to combustion products for which $T_\infty = 800^\circ\text{C}$ and $h = 22 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$.

(a) Determine the time of exposure required for the surface to reach the ignition temperature of 400°C.

Question 5.72 - SOLUTION

(a) In this scenario the thick oak wall can be treated as a semi-infinite solid with the following properties (evaluated at $T = 300 \text{ K}$): $\rho = 545 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $c = 2385 \text{ J/kg}$, $k = 0.17 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ and $\alpha = 1.31 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

Bear in mind that this situation corresponds to Case 3 of *Figure 5.7* on page **285**. Therefore **equation 5.63** should be employed. Knowing that

$$\frac{T(0,t) - T_i}{T_\infty - T_i} = \frac{400^\circ\text{C} - 25^\circ\text{C}}{800^\circ\text{C} - 25^\circ\text{C}} = 0.48$$

and that

$$\frac{x}{\sqrt{\alpha t}} = 0$$

it is possible to use *Figure 5.8* to extract the value of $\frac{h\sqrt{\alpha t}}{k}$ graphically.

$$\frac{h\sqrt{\alpha t}}{k} \approx 0.75$$

Therefore, rearranging for t should give that:

$$t = \left(\frac{0.75 \cdot 0.17 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}}{22 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K} \cdot (1.31 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s})^{0.5}} \right)^2 = 257 \text{ s}$$

Question 5.73

Standards for firewalls may be based on their thermal response to a prescribed radiant heat flux. Consider a 0.25-m-thick concrete wall ($\rho = 2300 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $c = 880 \text{ J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$, $k = 1.4 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$), which is at an initial temperature of $T_i = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and irradiated at one surface by lamps that provide a uniform heat flux of $q_s'' = 10^4 \text{ W/m}^2$. The absorptivity of the surface to the irradiation is $\alpha_s = 1.0$. If building code requirements dictate that the temperatures of the irradiated and back surfaces must not exceed 325°C and 25°C , respectively, after 30 min of heating, will the requirements be met?

Question 5.73 - SOLUTION

Semi-infinite solids are solids that extend to infinity in all but one direction and are characterised by a single identifiable surface. If a sudden change of conditions is imposed at this surface, transient, one-dimensional conduction will occur within the solid. The semi-infinite approximation can be made to finite geometries for the early portion of the transient if $Fo < 0.2$.

$\alpha = k/\rho c_p = 6.92 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, $t = 30 \text{ min} = 1800 \text{ s}$ and $L_c = 0.125 \text{ m}$. Therefore $Fo = 0.01993$ and the semi infinite approximation can be employed for this case.

Since we are dealing with a scenario of constant surface heat flux, the following formula should be employed (see page 287 textbook):

$$T(x, t) - T_i = \frac{2q_0''(\alpha t/\pi)^{1/2}}{k} \cdot e^{(-x^2/4\alpha t)} - \frac{q_0''x}{k} \cdot \text{erfc}\left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right)$$

By subbing in the correct values, these results are obtained:

$$T(0, 1800\text{s}) = 25^\circ\text{C} + 284.5^\circ\text{C} = 309.5^\circ\text{C} < 350^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T(0.25, 1800 \text{ s}) = 25^\circ\text{C} + 284.5^\circ\text{C} \cdot (3.58 \cdot 10^{-6}) - 1785.7^\circ\text{C} \cdot (\sim 0) \approx 25^\circ\text{C}$$

Hence it is clear that both requirements are met.

Question 2.5 (Drysdale)

A fire in a room rapidly raises the temperature of the surface of the walls and maintains them at 1000°C for a prolonged period. On the other side of one wall is a large warehouse, whose ambient temperature is normally 20°C. If the wall is solid brick, 200 mm thick, and retains its integrity, what would be the steady state temperature of the surface of the wall on the warehouse side? Assume that the thermal conductivity of the brick is independent of temperature and that the convective heat transfer coefficient at the wall is 12 W/m² · K. (Take $k_{brick} = 0.69$ W/m · K)

Question 2.5 (Drysdale) - SOLUTION

By reading the statement of the question carefully, it is clear that we have to work with resistances in order to solve the problem. Indeed, the first step consists of simplifying the scenario and representing it as a thermal circuit. In this case we are concerned only about two resistances: the one of the wall and the one of the ambient air.

It is therefore possible to employ the following equation:

$$q'' = \frac{T_h - T_\infty}{\frac{L}{k} + \frac{1}{h}}$$

It is now essential to remember that q'' is constant throughout the thermal network. Hence:

$$\frac{T_h - T_\infty}{\frac{L}{k} + \frac{1}{h}} = \frac{T_{warehouse} - T_\infty}{\frac{1}{h}} = h \cdot (T_{warehouse} - T_\infty)$$

ADDITIONAL FIRE RELATED QUESTIONS - BONUS

The above equation can be rearranged for $T_{warehouse}$ in the following way:

$$T_{warehouse} = \frac{1000^{\circ}\text{C} - 20^{\circ}\text{C}}{\left(\frac{0.2 \text{ m}}{0.69 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}} + \frac{1}{12 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}}\right) \cdot 12 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}} + 20^{\circ}\text{C} = 238.8^{\circ}\text{C}$$

Question 2.16-2.17 (Drysdale)

A building is totally involved in fire, but there is no external flaming. One wall, measuring 20 m long by 10 m high, has four symmetrically placed windows, each 6 m long by 2 m high.

(a) Assuming that the windows act as blackbody radiators at 1000°C , calculate the radiant heat flux 10 m from the building, where the radiant heat flux is a maximum. Assume that the receiver is parallel to the face of the building.

Drysdale, 2011

(b) Taking the building fire described above, what will the radiant heat flux be at a point 10 m from the building at ground level on a line perpendicular to the mid-point of the base of the wall? Assume that the receiver is parallel to the face of the building.

Question 2.5 (Drysdale) - SOLUTION

(a) The best way to start solving the part (a) is to re-sketch the scenario as following:

Therefore it can be deduced that $\phi_{ABCD} = 4\phi_{AJKL}$ and that $\phi_{ABCD} = 4(\phi_{AEGI} - \phi_{EGHL} - \phi_{FGIJ} + \phi_{FGHK})$. In order to calculate all the different view factors, we are going to make use of Table 2.8 on page **66** of the *Drysdale: 'An Introduction to Fire Dynamics'* textbook. For rectangle AEGI:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{3}{8} = 0.375$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{3 \cdot 8}{10^2} = 0.24$$

Therefore $\phi_{AEGI} = 0.053$.
For rectangle EGHL:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{2}{3} = 0.667$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 3}{10^2} = 0.06$$

Therefore $\phi_{EGHL} = 0.018$.
For rectangle FGIJ:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{1}{8} = 0.125$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{1 \cdot 8}{10^2} = 0.08$$

Therefore $\phi_{FGIJ} = 0.018$.
For rectangle FGHK:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{1 \cdot 2}{10^2} = 0.02$$

Therefore $\phi_{EGHL} = 0.006$.

Hence, $\phi_{ABCD} = 4(0.053 - 0.018 - 0.018 + 0.006) = 0.092$. It is now possible to calculate the radiant heat flux experienced 10 m away from the building:

$$q'' = \phi_{ABCD} \rho T^4 = (0.092) \cdot (5.67 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^4) \cdot (1000 + 273 \text{ K})^4 = 13700 \text{ W/m}^2$$

(b) For part (b), the scenario should be simplified as shown below:

From the image above it can be deduced that $\phi_{ABCD} = 2\phi_{AOPQ} + 2\phi_{DLMN}$ and that $\phi_{ABCD} = 2(\phi_{AEIK} - \phi_{EIJQ} - \phi_{FIKO} + \phi_{FIJP}) + 2(\phi_{GIKN} - \phi_{GIJM} - \phi_{HIKD} + \phi_{HIJL})$.
For rectangle AEIK:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{6}{8} = 0.75$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{6 \cdot 8}{10^2} = 0.48$$

Therefore $\phi_{AEIK} = 0.093$.

For rectangle EIJQ:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{2}{8} = 0.25$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 8}{10^2} = 0.16$$

Therefore $\phi_{EIJQ} = 0.036$.

For rectangle FIKO:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{6}{6} = 1$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{6 \cdot 6}{10^2} = 0.36$$

Therefore $\phi_{FIKO} = 0.078$.

For rectangle FIJP:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{2}{6} = 0.33$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 6}{10^2} = 0.12$$

Therefore $\phi_{FIJP} = 0.030$.

For rectangle GIKN:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{4}{6} = 0.67$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{4 \cdot 6}{10^2} = 0.24$$

Therefore $\phi_{GIKN} = 0.057$.

For rectangle GIJM:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{2}{4} = 0.5$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 4}{10^2} = 0.08$$

Therefore $\phi_{GIJM} = 0.023$.

For rectangle HIKD:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{2}{8} = 0.25$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 8}{10^2} = 0.16$$

Therefore $\phi_{HIKD} = 0.036$.

For rectangle HIJL:

$$S = \frac{L_1}{L_2} = \frac{2}{2} = 1$$

$$\alpha = \frac{L_1 \cdot L_2}{D^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 2}{10^2} = 0.04$$

Therefore $\phi_{HIJL} = 0.012$.

Hence, $\phi_{ABCD} = 2(0.093 - 0.036 - 0.078 + 0.030) + 2(0.057 - 0.023 - 0.036 + 0.012) = 0.038$.

It is now possible to calculate the radiant heat flux experienced 10 m away from the building:

$$q'' = \phi_{ABCD} \rho T^4 = (0.038) \cdot (5.67 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^4) \cdot (1000 + 273 \text{ K})^4 = 5658 \text{ W/m}^2$$

Radiation example 1 (Drysdale)

A plate of 1x1 m area is initially at $T_0 = 25^\circ\text{C}$. It is a grey body with $\epsilon = 0.8$. It is heated internally with 50 kW. Convective cooling coefficient is $h = 5 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$. The ambient temperature is T_0 . Find the equilibrium temperature of the plate.

Radiation example 1 (Drysdale) - SOLUTION

Start with an energy balance: $\dot{E}_{in} = \dot{E}_{out}$. This brings to:

$$\text{Heat in} = \text{internal heating} + \text{radiation from surrounding} = 50000 \text{ W} + 2A\epsilon\sigma T_0^4$$

*where the two above appears because the plate irradiates heat from both of its faces

$$\text{Heat out} = \text{emission at the surface} + \text{convective cooling} = 2A\epsilon\sigma T_a^4 + 2Ah(T_a - T_0)$$

Therefore for equilibrium:

$$50000 \text{ W} + 2A\epsilon\sigma T_0^4 = 2A\epsilon\sigma T_a^4 + 2Ah(T_a - T_0)$$

$$50000 \text{ W} = 2A\epsilon\sigma(T_a^4 - T_0^4) + 2Ah(T_a - T_0)$$

You can sub in the values and solve the above equation either via Newton Raphson, bisection or secant method. The answer you should get is: $T_a = 841 \text{ K}$. Below you can find the python code that brings you to the answer.

ADDITIONAL FIRE RELATED QUESTIONS - BONUS

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

#use the bisection method to find the intersection between two functions
#first define the two functions

#write a code to implement the Bisection method
def Bisection(a, b, tolerance):
    #check if you have picked two correct initial guesses
    if Func(a) * Func(b) > 0:
        print('Choose other two initial guesses')
    else:
        #initialise the error and the iterations
        iterations = 0
        while abs(a - b) > tolerance:
            xnew = (a + b) / 2
            if Func(xnew) * Func(a) < 0:
                #update the interval
                b = xnew
                #update th enumber of iterations
                iterations += 1
            elif Func(xnew) * Func(b) < 0:
                #update the interval
                a = xnew
                #update th enumber of iterations
                iterations += 1
        sol = (a + b) / 2
        return sol, iterations

#define the function you want to test 'Bisection' with
def Func(x):
    f = 50000 - 2 * 1 * 0.8 * (5.67 * 10**(-8))*((x**4) - (298**4))- 2 * 1 * 5 * (x - 298)
    return f

#choose two initial intervals
a = 0
b = 1000
x = np.arange(-2, 7, 0.1)
y = Func(x)
s = Bisection(a, b, 0.0001)
print(s)
```

Radiation example 2 (Drysdale)

Now plate a is heated internally and cooled the same way as in **Radiation Example 1**, but in addition there is now a parallel identical plate b , 0.15 m away. Plate b is heated by radiation from plate a , which in turn receives radiation from b . Find the equilibrium temperature for plates a and b . Configuration factors are $\phi_{a,b} = \phi_{b,a} = 0.75$.

Radiation example 2 (Drysdale) - SOLUTION

Start with an energy balance concerning plate a .

$$\text{Heat in} = \text{internal heating} + \text{irradiation from Plate } b \text{ and surrounding} =$$

$$50000 \text{ W} + A\phi_{b,a}\epsilon^2\sigma T_b^4 + A(2 - \phi_{b,a})\epsilon\sigma T_0^4$$

$$\text{Heat out} = \text{emission from Plate } a \text{ + convective cooling} =$$

$$2A\epsilon\sigma T_a^4 + 2Ah(T_a - T_0)$$

Therefore,

$$50000 \text{ W} + A\phi_{b,a}\epsilon^2\sigma T_b^4 + A(2 - \phi_{b,a})\epsilon\sigma T_0^4 = 2A\epsilon\sigma T_a^4 + 2Ah(T_a - T_0)$$

For plate b instead:

$$\text{Heat in} = \text{internal heating} + \text{irradiation from Plate } b \text{ and surrounding} =$$

$$A\phi_{a,b}\epsilon^2\sigma T_a^4 + A(2 - \phi_{a,b})\epsilon\sigma T_0^4$$

$$\text{Heat out} = \text{emission from Plate } b + \text{convective cooling} = 2A\epsilon\sigma T_b^4 + 2Ah(T_b - T_0)$$

Therefore,

$$A\phi_{a,b}\epsilon^2\sigma T_a^4 + A(2 - \phi_{a,b})\epsilon\sigma T_0^4 = 2A\epsilon\sigma T_b^4 + 2Ah(T_b - T_0)$$

We now have a system of two equations where the only unknown are T_a and T_b . As the system is non linear, it is wise to employ the Newton Raphson method to solve it. By running the code on the following page on python, you should find that: $T_a \approx 855$ K and $T_b \approx 602$ K.

ADDITIONAL FIRE RELATED QUESTIONS - BONUS

```
@author: Francesco Riviuccio
"""

import numpy as np

#write a function to determine the solutions of system of non-linear equations, using the Newton-Raphson method
#remember that you need two functions and Jacobian matrix to solve this system
def mySystem(hold, Func, Func2, J, tolerance):
    #understand how many equations you have by inspecting the lenght of the initial guesses you have to make
    n = len(hold)
    iterations = 0
    #set the tolerance
    error = 10
    while error > tolerance:
        hnew = np.zeros((n, 1))
        #create an array where you store the functions evaluations with the previous guess
        ar = np.array([ [Func(hold[0], hold[1]), Func2(hold[0], hold[1]) ], dtype = float )
        #calculate the new guess by inverting the Jacobian matrix (evaluated at hold) and multiplying it by the 'ar' matrix
        hnewx = hold[0, 0] - np.dot( J( hold[0], hold[1] ), ar )[0]
        hnewy = hold[1, 0] - np.dot( J( hold[0], hold[1] ), ar )[1]
        error = max([abs((hnewx - hold[0, 0]) / hnewx), abs((hnewy - hold[1, 0]) / hnewy)])
        #-----#
        #append the results to hnew
        hnew[0] = hnewx
        hnew[1] = hnewy
        hold = np.copy(hnew)
        iterations += 1
    return hnew, iterations

#define the set of non linear equations you want to test the function with (including the jacobian)
def J(x, y):
    A = np.array([[4 * 1 * 0.75 * (0.8**2) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (x**3), \
        -4 * 2 * 1 * (0.8) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (y**3) - 2 * 1 * 5]\
        , [-4 * 2 * 1 * (0.8) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (x**3) - 2 * 1 * 5,\
        4 * 1 * 0.75 * (0.8**2) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (y**3)],\
        dtype = float)
    A = np.linalg.inv(A)
    return A

def Func(x, y):
    f = 50000 + 1 * 0.75 * (0.8**2) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (x**4) + \
        1 * (2 - 0.75) * (0.8) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (298**4) - 2 * 1 * 0.8 * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (y**4) \
        - 2 * 1 * 5 * (y - 298)
    return f

def Func2(x, y):
    f2 = 1 * 0.75 * (0.8**2) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (y**4) + \
        1 * (2 - 0.75) * (0.8) * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (298**4) - \
        2 * 1 * 0.8 * (5.67 * 10**(-8)) * (x**4) - 2 * 1 * 5 * (x - 298)
    return f2

#set the initial guesses
T_b = 1
T_a = 2
hold = np.array([[T_b], [T_a]], dtype = float)
s = mySystem(hold, Func, Func2, J, 0.00001)
print('X = ' + str(s[0][0]))
print('Y = ' + str(s[0][1]))
print('Number of iterations needed: ' + str(s[1]))
```